

ANALYSIS OF ACUTE BACTERIAL CONJUNCTIVITIS IN YOUNG CHILDREN AND YOUNG ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

As a result of the microbiological investigations performed during the study, algorithms for the microbiological and mycological analysis of bacterial conjunctivitis in adults were developed. The advantages of these algorithms included the possibility of designing a structured plan for microbiological and mycological investigations, implementing it step by step, and delivering reliable analytical results in a timely manner. These algorithms for microbiological and mycological analysis are being recommended for the first time for the purpose of microbiological confirmation of the diagnosis of bacterial conjunctivitis and are convenient for laboratory investigations. It was established that the mucus of the conjunctival sac is rich in nonspecific defense factors of the body, including β -lysozyme, immunoglobulins—particularly secretory immunoglobulin A (sIgA)—and other protective factors..

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Aim of the study. The aim of the study was to analyze the biological characteristics of the causative agents of acute bacterial conjunctivitis among children and adults and to assess their variability.

Materials and methods. Among the pediatric patients, girls accounted for $52.6 \pm 11.5\%$ ($n = 10$), while boys accounted for $47.4 \pm 11.5\%$ ($n = 9$). Among adult patients, women constituted $46.5 \pm 7.6\%$ ($n = 20$), and men constituted $53.5 \pm 7.6\%$ ($n = 23$). The

bacteriological study was conducted at the Educational and Scientific Bacteriological Laboratory of the Department of Microbiology, Virology and Immunology of Bukhara State Medical Institute. Conjunctival discharge, used as biological material, was collected during the development of the purulent-inflammatory process in compliance with aseptic rules. All medications and medical procedures were discontinued 5–6 hours before sampling for bacteriological examination. The biological material was collected in accordance with technical and biological safety regulations and then transported to the bacteriological laboratory for further investigation.

Results. During the study, 16 strains belonging to *Streptococcus* spp. were identified as monocultures. Of these, 14 strains belonged to *Streptococcus haemolyticus*, while 2 strains were identified as *Streptococcus pyogenes* — group A streptococci, or β -hemolytic streptococci. These strains demonstrated genus-specific morphological characteristics in 100% of cases. Their cultural and biological characteristics were defined by the absence of catalase activity, indicating catalase-negative strains, and by the presence of hemolytic activity. Both biological features were observed in all strains (100%). In differentiating them from *Staphylococcus* spp., attention was paid not only to their morphological characteristics, but also to the two above-mentioned biological properties.

It is known that the family *Enterobacteriaceae* includes both beneficial human symbionts—saprophytes—and pathogenic microorganisms capable of causing disease in humans, such as *Salmonella* spp., *Shigella* spp., and others. In recent decades, diseases caused by opportunistic pathogenic microorganisms belonging to this family have also become an increasingly relevant problem. Examples include *Citrobacter* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Enterobacter* spp., *Proteus* spp., and *Providencia* spp. To date, 10 genera, 115 species, and 19 subspecies of the family *Enterobacteriaceae* are known, while the taxonomic position of some of them in the international classification has not yet been fully resolved. This creates certain difficulties in the identification of strains. The large number of genera and species within the family *Enterobacteriaceae* also complicates their differentiation. As a result, strain identification requires considerable time and financial resources, increases the demand for highly qualified specialists, and reduces the likelihood of obtaining an accurate bacteriological diagnosis.

Conclusion. Thus, the strains belonging to the family *Enterobacteriaceae* isolated from the biological material of patients with bacterial conjunctivitis — including 3 strains of *Escherichia coli* and 2 strains of *Proteus* spp. — were typical strains characteristic of their respective genera and species according to the main biological properties studied.